

The Critical Exploration of Visibly Invisible Life of Nomads as Illustrated in *Ekathari: An Autobiography of a Nomad* by Kuppe Nagaraj

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Abstract:

The autobiography *Ekathari: An Autobiography of a Nomad* by Kuppe Nagaraja explores the challenges faced by Nomads, who have frequently been marginalized in geographic, economic, and political contexts within post-colonial states. The author, though a vivid narrative style describes that the nomadic lifestyle is often stigmatized as 'backward' in the pursuit of nation-building and economic development. A primary criticism against nomads revolves around their spatial mobility, which is perceived as an "unfettered physical environment across the landscape" during the activities of a mobile economy, leading to a lack of engagement in social relations within specific sites and communities.

In South India, particularly in Andhra Pradesh, non-pastoral nomads heavily rely on rural village communities but tend to remain aloof from participating in village affairs. This paper aims to address significant issues related to the conceptualization of the nomadic way of life and its associated challenges within the evolving social fabric. Nomadism is often linked to an occupational description that defines a particular caste or community, with limited exploration of the broader conceptualization of nomadism itself. The intricate descriptions of nomadic communities predominantly focus on their occupational specialization.

Key Words: Nomads, Ekathari, Dombi Dasas, Jolige, Denotified and Nomadic Tribes

Very little is known about the lives of people constantly in motion, struggling to make a living— the Nomads. In India, the nomadic population is estimated to be around 80 million. Nomads are ethnic or socio-professional groups that migrate in large or small clan formations, seeking livelihoods within their community, across a nation, or even beyond international borders. Unfortunately, these communities lack constitutional safeguards. Efforts should be made to encourage nomadic communities to settle in specific locations, allowing them to integrate into the mainstream of society. The removal of material barriers is essential for their development. Narratives of nomads often reveal experiences of powerlessness, alienation, and a loss of control over their daily lives. Many live in extreme poverty, with average food intake falling significantly below nutritional requirements, and they often face harassment from law enforcement. Nagaraja's opening lines testify to the poverty endured by the nomads:

Appa owned nothing. There was nothing in the whole wide world that he could call his own. He was said to have come from the north [of Mysore]. With no place of his own to stay, he wandered from place to place with a jolige² hanging from his shoulder, seeking alms as per family tradition. Alms seeking was the way of life he inherited from his forefathers, the Dombi Dasas. He eked out a living by singing ballads, presenting plays, and narrating religious stories, in addition to seeking alms. Appa—and along with him, our family—would wander to places that received good rains. He would stay at any place that he judged safe for the family.⁴ Any place that would offer the space to pitch his tent or appeared

to offer a better bargain for eking out a living for a few days would become his home. Whenever and wherever Appa decided to stop, Avva would set up a hearth within no time to cook our meals. This hearth would be made of three stones and would burn firewood collected in the vicinity. (p.2)

Nomadism is a global phenomenon encompassing ethnic or socio-professional groups that travel and migrate in large or small clan formations in search of livelihood within a community, a nation, or even across international boundaries. A contemporary definition of "Nomadism" denotes any form of existence characterized by the absence of a fixed domicile. In India, 8.08% of the population is classified as Scheduled Tribes, and of the total tribal population of 67.7 million, 6.2% (41.99 million) are dispersed in varying concentrations in the state of Andhra Pradesh. Presently, Andhra Pradesh is home to nearly 32 million tribes and 50 million nomads and other backward communities. Nationally, there are about 8 crore Denotified and Nomadic Tribes (DNTs) people, with around one crore (10 million) residing in Andhra Pradesh. The state hosts approximately 35 DNT communities, including Piccukaguntlu, Badlasanta, Saradakandru, Viramushtivaru, Bavanilu, Birannalavaru, Gallasuddulu, Dasaralu, Jandamulu, Kommuvaru, Mallikharjunudu, among others, which are Telugu Nomads. Lambadis/Sugalis represent non-Telugu nomads in the region. This is justified by Nagaraja himself in the following words:

Interestingly, nature seemed to resist our efforts to settle in one place. The year after we established our settlement, the ponds dried up completely, deprived of rain, leaving no water source for our cattle. The looming drought threatened our existence, dependent as it was on farmers having enough grain reserves. Our survival hung in the balance. Seeking alms

became increasingly difficult, and the drought-induced hardships led to a decline in interest in our performances. Concerns about the uncertain future mounted among our people, including Appa and Avva. Following our customary practice, considering the dire circumstances, thoughts turned to migration as a means to escape starvation, moving towards regions blessed with rainfall. (p.7)

The passage describes the challenges faced by a community that had settled in one place. Despite their efforts to establish a stable home, they encountered a significant setback when the ponds dried up due to the absence of rain, leaving no water for their cattle. The ensuing drought posed a serious threat to their survival, particularly because their well-being depended on the availability of grain reserves held by local farmers. With seeking alms becoming increasingly difficult and a decline in interest in their performances, the community faced mounting concerns about an uncertain future. In response to these challenges, the community, including individuals named Appa and Avva, considered reverting to their traditional practice of migration. This migration was viewed as a strategy to escape the looming threat of starvation and find regions where rainfall was more abundant, offering better prospects for their survival.

A critical overview of nomadic life involves an examination of the challenges, cultural richness, and societal perceptions associated with a lifestyle characterized by constant movement and absence of a fixed domicile. Nomadic communities, historically marginalized and often misunderstood, offer a unique lens through which to explore the complexities of identity, survival, and resilience. Nomadic life poses several challenges, primarily rooted in the constant need for mobility. Access to resources such as water, food, and shelter becomes unpredictable, making survival a perpetual struggle.

Additionally, nomadic communities often face discrimination and exclusion, with limited access to education, healthcare, and other essential services. The absence of legal safeguards leaves them vulnerable to exploitation and harassment, amplifying the difficulties of their way of life:

Appa was named Singaiah by his parents, but people came to identify him with the clown character he enacted in the plays. Over time, Singaiah became Kodangaiah (“Mr. Clown”) in all official records, and Singaiah was forgotten forever! (p.4)

Nomadic cultures are often characterized by a deep connection to nature, resourcefulness, and a strong sense of community. The mobility of these communities fosters a unique relationship with the environment, and their traditions, languages, and oral histories contribute to the rich tapestry of human diversity. Nomadic life reflects an adaptive and sustainable approach to living in harmony with nature, showcasing resilience in the face of adversity. Despite the cultural wealth embedded in nomadic life, societal perceptions have often been marked by stereotypes, bias, and a lack of understanding. Nomads are sometimes stigmatized as 'backward' or 'primitive,' reinforcing a cycle of marginalization. This lack of recognition contributes to their social and economic exclusion, hindering efforts to address the challenges they face. Nomadic lifestyles historically embraced sustainable practices, minimizing their environmental impact. However, modern challenges, such as climate change, increased competition for resources, and restrictive government policies, have intensified the difficulties faced by nomadic communities. Encroachment on their traditional lands further threatens their way of life, raising questions about the sustainability of nomadic

practices in the contemporary world. Therefore, a critical overview of nomadic life requires a nuanced understanding that goes beyond simplistic stereotypes. By acknowledging the challenges, celebrating cultural richness, and challenging societal perceptions, we can foster a more inclusive dialogue that appreciates the contributions of nomadic communities and addresses the systemic issues they encounter.

The Metaphor of Hunger

The metaphor of 'hunger' in the text extends beyond its literal meaning, evolving into a powerful symbol with profound philosophical dimensions. When viewed from a broader perspective, the life of Dalits is portrayed as being fundamentally shaped by a hunger for various forms of identity—ranging from individual and familial to religious, economic, social, and political identities. This hunger for identity becomes a central theme, influencing the experiences and struggles of the Dalit community. The hunger for identity suggests a profound yearning for recognition and affirmation. Dalits, historically marginalized and subjected to discrimination, seek to establish and assert their individual and collective identities. This hunger is driven by a desire to break free from societal constraints and gain acknowledgment for their humanity, culture, and contributions.

The metaphorical hunger of the high-caste community becomes a driving force behind the exploitation faced by Dalits. This exploitation operates at multiple levels—individual, social, economic, and political. The imbalance of power created by this hunger for dominance perpetuates social injustices, economic disparities, and political marginalization, all of which contribute to the miseries and toil endured by the Dalit community. The text highlights the particularly tragic dimension of the hunger metaphor through the victimization of Dalit women. The hunger for dominance and

control leads to the exploitation and oppression of women within the community. Their suffering is portrayed as a direct consequence of the insatiable hunger of the higher castes for maintaining supremacy and asserting authority over marginalized groups.

The overarching hunger theme reflects the Dalits' yearning for survival in the face of systemic oppression. It encompasses the struggle for recognition, dignity, and rights. The hunger for basic human needs, justice, and acknowledgment fuels the resilience and resistance within the Dalit community. The metaphor of 'hunger' serves as a complex and multi-faceted symbol in the text, encapsulating the existential challenges faced by Dalits. It goes beyond the physical need for sustenance to represent a deep and pervasive hunger for identity, justice, and survival in the face of systemic oppression and discrimination.

Appa's jolige was the kalpavruksha, the all-provider, to us. It had three compartments. In one, grains like ragi (finger millet), wheat, and paddy were collected. A second compartment was set aside for various flours, cooked rice, and rotis. The third was for various pulses, chillies, and other spices. It was our akshayapathre, our inexhaustible providing bowl.

Occasionally,

Appa would hunt some animals or birds on the way back from his alms-seeking sorties. The materials needed to trap these animals and birds too were ever present in his jolige. Avva used to eagerly check the contents of the bag as soon as Appa returned home and quickly sort the contents. First, she would sieve the flour out, and then she would segregate the various pulses and spices. She would then prepare ragi balls and sambar. By the time she finished, we would be fast asleep and would have to be woken up

and fed. After this, she would eat whatever was left and go to sleep. This was her routine. (p.5)

Motherhood in Dalit Literature

The concept of motherhood in Dalit literature often carries complex layers of meaning and symbolism. In the provided passage, Avva's role as a mother is depicted within the specific context of Dalit life, offering insights into the challenges and sacrifices that Dalit mothers navigate. Avva's act of eagerly checking and sorting the contents of the bag reflects the harsh reality of economic scarcity that many Dalit families face. Despite limited resources, her dedication to ensuring a proper meal for her family showcases the resilience and nurturing nature of Dalit mothers. The emphasis on sieving flour and segregating pulses and spices suggests a meticulous effort to make the most of available provisions.

Avva's routine of preparing ragi balls and sambar after the family has already gone to sleep highlights the sacrificial nature of her motherhood. The late-night cooking, waking up the children to feed them, and then consuming whatever is left indicate a selfless commitment to ensuring her family's well-being even at the cost of her own comfort and rest. The repetition of this routine paints a picture of everyday resilience. Avva's commitment to sustaining her family becomes a daily act of resistance against the challenges imposed by economic hardships. This routine becomes symbolic of the larger struggles faced by Dalit mothers who navigate adversity to provide for their families.

We, the four children, were taken care of with Avva's earnings from manual labour and Appa's earnings from his drama performances and alms seeking.

Avva had never learnt skills required to carry out family's customary professions like singing or playing ekathari etc., and Appa knew no agriculture or field labour. Appa's way of working was to dress up, hang the jolige on his shoulder, and venture out seeking alms with a string instrument such as the ekathari. Usually, three to four people used to go out together to seek alms. However, Appa used to occasionally go alone too. (p.4)

The passage captures motherhood not as an abstract concept but as a lived experience embedded in the day-to-day realities of Dalit life. Avva's actions are grounded in the material conditions and social context of her existence, emphasizing the tangible and pragmatic aspects of motherhood. Through Avva's efforts, the passage subtly explores the intersectionality of motherhood and Dalit identity. The challenges she faces, the scarcity she navigates, and the resilience she exhibits are shaped by her identity as a Dalit woman. This intersectionality adds depth to the portrayal of motherhood, acknowledging the specific struggles faced by Dalit mothers. In Dalit literature, the concept of motherhood often becomes a lens through which the broader socio-economic and cultural dimensions of Dalit life are examined. Avva's routine exemplifies the strength, resilience, and selflessness associated with Dalit motherhood, contributing to a nuanced understanding of maternal experiences within the context of marginalization and discrimination.

The passage also highlights the intersectionality of oppression faced by Dalits, emphasizing the layers of subjugation based on caste, class, and gender. It explores the ways in which Dalit narratives, particularly in autobiographies and creative writings, bring forth unique representations of social stratification, often using food as a significant element in expressing identity and negotiating life. Dalit literature probes

into the intricate interplay of caste, class, and gender, acknowledging the complex structure of forces that shape the lives of marginalized communities. The text recognizes that the intensity and manifestation of caste-based practices vary across regions and are influenced by geographical and ecological factors.

The focus on food in Dalit narratives serves as a powerful symbol of identity. Detailed descriptions of the food cooked and consumed in day-to-day life become integral to characterizing the experiences and cultural practices of Dalit individuals. Food acts as a medium through which the characters assert their identity and navigate their existence. The inclusion of elaborate culinary details in Dalit narratives signifies the importance of the mundane aspects of life. Descriptions of food preparation and consumption contribute to a rich portrayal of the characters' everyday experiences, offering readers a nuanced understanding of the challenges and joys embedded in their daily routines. The association of food with ritualistic practices adds another layer to the cultural connotation of dietary habits within Dalit communities. Dietary restrictions and preferences become not only personal choices but also markers of cultural identity and resistance against oppressive structures.

Food serves as a metaphor through which Dalit characters navigate and construct their identities. The act of cooking, sharing meals, and engaging in culinary practices becomes a means of resistance and self-expression within a society marked by discrimination. The passage thus underscores the significance of food in Dalit literature as a dynamic element intertwined with identity, cultural practices, and resistance. By focusing on the daily rituals and culinary details, Dalit narratives offer readers a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of marginalized communities and the various dimensions of their struggle against social inequalities.

Life Without a Permanent Abode

The autobiography paints a vivid picture of a nomadic existence, emphasizing the characters' wandering lifestyle, which reflects the circumstances of a nomadic community. The recurrent theme of moving from one place to another suggests a purposeless, meandering pattern, characteristic of a nomadic way of life. In the narrative, a group of people is depicted, symbolizing a larger tribal community, whose existence is marked by constant movement. The nomadic lifestyle portrayed in the autobiography becomes a canvas upon which the impact of various socio-economic factors is painted. One notable influence is the encroachment of modernization, wherein traditional nomadic practices clash with the values and dynamics of a rapidly changing world.

The narrative suggests that the nomadic community is not immune to the forces of commercialization and capitalism, which disrupt their traditional way of life. The encroachment of modern values introduces complexities into their nomadic existence, challenging established norms and practices. Furthermore, the narrative acknowledges the influence of external factors such as the economy, natural disasters, and the struggle for survival. These elements contribute to the nomadic community's vulnerability, shaping their movements and decisions. The nomads are portrayed as navigating a dynamic and challenging landscape where traditional practices intersect with the pressures of a changing world. Essentially, *Ekathari: An Autobiography of a Nomad* unfolds a narrative where nomadic life is not just a cultural practice but also a response to, and negotiation with, the evolving external forces that impact the community's survival and existence.

Appa—and along with him, our family—would wander to places that received good rains. He would stay at any place that he judged safe for the family. Any place that would offer the space to pitch his tent or appeared to offer a better bargain for eking out a living for a few days would become his home. Whenever and wherever Appa decided to stop, Avva would set up a hearth within no time to cook our meals. This hearth would be made of three stones and would burn firewood collected in the vicinity. (p.2)

The opening passage of the autobiography vividly portrays the nomadic existence of the protagonist's family, encapsulating the essence of a life without a permanent abode. The narrative unfolds a transient lifestyle where Appa, the patriarch, leads the family from one place to another based on the availability of essential resources, especially rainfall. The absence of a fixed dwelling signifies the perpetual movement characterizing the lives of nomads. The act of wandering to places with good rains becomes a survival strategy for the family. Appa's decision on where to settle temporarily is guided by safety considerations and the potential for securing a means of livelihood. The narrative captures the adaptability and resilience inherent in a nomadic lifestyle, where the family embraces any place judged suitable for their immediate needs.

Avva, the matriarch, plays a central role in establishing a semblance of home wherever they stop. Her ability to set up a hearth quickly signifies the resourcefulness required to sustain daily life on the move. The makeshift hearth, constructed from three stones, becomes a symbolic anchor, offering a place for the family to cook their meals amid the transient landscapes. The portrayal of nomadic life in this passage highlights the impermanence, adaptability, and resourcefulness inherent in the daily struggles of those without a fixed residence. It encapsulates a way of life where the search for a

better bargain and the quest for sustenance dictate the family's movements, making each temporary stop a unique chapter in their nomadic journey.

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